

Narrow Market Business Level Strategies Performance of Micro and Small Enterprises

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Adote Philemon Addo**-School of Economics and Management-Jiangxi Science and Technology Normal University Email: adotephilemon@gmail.com

⁽²⁾**Ibn Ali Issah Kulo**-School of International Trade and Economics-Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics

Abstract

Contrary to popular belief, there has been little empirical research on the impact of cost-cutting and product diversification on the success of micro- and small-sized businesses, therefore this study is needed to fill the knowledge gap. With a focus on salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County, the goal of this research was to see how generic limited market strategies affected the performance of small enterprises, particularly micro and tiny ones. The study used a descriptive research design, using Jakarta County's 279 salons and beauty spas as the study's target population and a sample size of 165 participants. Quantitative data was collected by a standardized questionnaire. Research shows that at a 5 percent level of significance, focused cost strategy has moderately positive significant impact on micro and small firms' performance, whereas focused differentiation strategy has moderately positive significant impact. In the research, it is recommended that micro and small businesses maintain their knowledge, innovation, and constant improvement, as well as design methods for creating competitive, inexpensive, and appealing rates, as well as plans for premium items in a specialised limited market

Keywords: *Focused cost leadership strategy, Focused differentiation strategy, Generic strategies, Micro and small enterprises performance, Narrow market, Performance, Salons and beauty spas*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Indonesia, a topographically assorted country with a populace of 207 million, has had the option to accomplish high paces of monetary development. Notwithstanding, in spite of thirty years of fast development, the monetary design is as yet in light of casual or customary exercises in which a great many people are utilized. Indonesia's workforce is developing at a considerably quicker yearly rate (2.7 percent) than the populace all in all (1.6 percent) (World Bank 2000). The public authority of Indonesia is confronted with a test of giving long haul practical business and pay openings for the developing provincial workforce. The advancement of Miniature and Little Ventures (MSEs) as a technique to advance work in rustic regions has gotten impressive ongoing consideration in Indonesia, just as in other emerging nations. Ongoing financial choppiness and worries with developing monetary and social imbalances in Indonesia has invigorated conversations of means and goals of government strategies in regards to independent companies (Singh et al. 1999). The possible commitment of MSEs to producing work and pay in thickly populated country spaces of Asia has been archived (Liedholm, McPherson, and Chuta 1994). Their advancement is viewed as a method of giving guide to poor people and setting out work open doors for the under-utilized (Humphrey and Schmitz 1996).

Limited scope business visionaries in Makassar, a port city of more than 1.1 million individuals on the island of Sulawesi, Eastern Indonesia, work in an environment of financial difference and political vulnerability (Badan Pusat Statistik 2004). Regardless of fast monetary development preceding the 1997 financial political emergency, Indonesia keeps on encountering sharp territorial disparities, Eastern Indonesia being among the most unfortunate. This neediness is generally because of an Inward/External Island polarity comprehensively partitioning fabricating from asset extraction (Forbes 1986; Drake 1989; Monitoring 1998). Bunching of medium and huge scope firms on Java, essentially in the Jakarta area, has settled in this pattern. For sure, while Java, Bali, and Sumatra have profited from assembling via foundation improvement and private speculation,

Eastern Indonesia has grieved (Schwarz 1994). Makassar is the capital and managerial community for the region of South Sulawesi, and home to four primary ethnic gatherings, the Makassar (40%), Bugis (30%), Mandar (5%), and Toraja (5%). Chinese (3%) and a blend of Javanese and those from the External Islands (17%) address the rest of the populace as per neighborhood government gauges (key witness interviews 1997, 2003). These social outlines are crucial to grasping life in Makassar where adat (customs or customs) is a basic element of nearby societies, with an extraordinary adat relating to each gathering (Kahn 1980). By overseeing connections among individuals in organizations of social relations and giving a model of OK conduct inside nearby social limits, adapt is a vital effect on the regular financial conditions of business visionaries in the city (Kahn 1980; Turner 2003, 2005). Inside this specific situation, little undertakings have arisen as a basic wellspring of vocations for huge number of individuals in Makassar. Without a doubt, such undertakings have been progressively supported as a method by which fringe spaces of non-industrial nations might further develop creation result and general turn of events (Schmitz 1989; Slope 1997). A scope of conceivable reasons support this hopeful examination. Little endeavors address seedbeds for native business venture assembling in any case unstimulated capital. They are work concentrated, utilizing more work per unit of capital than enormous undertakings, and they can improve native innovative learning while at the same time adding to the decentralization of industry. Moreover, by using dominantly nearby assets, limited scope ventures have low unfamiliar trade necessities, and add to a more evenhanded conveyance of pay and abundance (Schmitz 1989; Alexander and Alexander 2000; Turner 2003). The study was informed by the Porter's generic strategy model and the Ansoff Model as a theoretical framework guides applicable to every stage of the research process, including the problem definition, literature review, methodology, presentation and discussion of the findings, and the conclusions reached. This theoretical framework aided in the development of the conceptual framework. The main objective of this study was to assess the influence of narrow market business level strategies on the performance of MSEs with a focus on salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County and to specifically seek to; To establish the influence of focused cost strategy on the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County. To find out the effect of focused differentiation strategy on the performance salons and beauty spas in Jakarta.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Micro and Small Enterprises in Java

All things considered, this article features the significance of nationality in friendly capital arrangement in the Indonesian setting. It tends to the negative just as sure sides of social capital—elements regularly disregarded in friendly capital examinations (Portes and Landolt 2000; Woolcock and Narayan 2000; Radcliffe 2004). Besides, it investigates the connections between friendly capital and the neighborhood political economy, "a topic just pitifully expounded in both occupation and social capital conversations" (Bebbington et al. 2006, 1963). Conversational key source interviews with pertinent nongovernmental association representatives, government authorities, and scholastics were embraced during both time spans. How unique social capital structures helped or thwarted explicit ventures is inspected, with specific consideration paid to the job of nationality in these elements. All in all, I basically think about the repercussions of the arrangement of social capital for the eventual fate of these occupations, taking note of likewise the essential requirement for nearby ecological components to be fused into such examinations.

2.2. Livelihoods, Social Capital, and Small Enterprises

An enthusiasm for the means by which vocations are shaped and supported offers bits of knowledge into how family individuals build a living inside the particular settings in which they work. While admittance to monetary capital is fundamental, regular, physical, human, and social capital, alongside the techniques important to amalgamate these, are through and through imperative to the constitution of livelihoods (Chambers and Conway 1991; Ellis 1998).⁵ For some, poor in non-industrial nations, summoning a scope of capital sorts assists with maintaining and even differentiate their occupations, subsequently working on their way of life. It is one such center nonmaterial resource, social capital, that frames the focal point of this review due to its focal

job in supporting limited scope undertakings on occasion when different types of capital—regularly those more unmistakable are restricted or past the range of people (cf. Grootaert 1999).

2.3 The Fundamentals of Social Capital

As an idea for considering the assets accessible to people and gatherings through friendly associations and relations, social capital has been advocated lately in much advancement writing. Agreement has arisen that fundamental commitments to the underlying conceptualizing of social capital advanced from three figures, in particular Pierre Bourdieu (1986) on types of capital, James Coleman (1987, 1988, 1990) on training, and Robert Putnam (1993, 1995) on urban investment. An expansive conceptualization in this way portrays social capital as fusing key parts of social association, for example, "trust, standards, and organizations" bringing about upgraded monetary execution and the capacity to adjust decidedly to a particular climate (Putnam 1993, 167). All the more explicitly, as characterized by Lin (2001, 55), "social capital spotlights on the assets inserted in one's interpersonal organization and how admittance to and utilization of such assets benefit the singular's activities." Attempting to explain the different translations of social capital, Woolcock and Narayan (2000) have offered four applied classes. In the first place, the communitarian view, likening social capital with neighborhood associations like clubs and affiliations, puts a positive twist on friendly capital, having a tendency to disregard its adverse consequences. At long last, the cooperative energy view unites thoughts from both the organizations and institutional classifications (Woolcock and Narayan 2000). Fighting that these ideas will generally work at explicit scales, Beugelsdijk and Smulders (2003) recommend that the organizations an individual has a place with work at the miniature or meso-level, while the differential social capital gifts of countries or locales influence levels of vote based system and financial development at the large scale (see likewise Grootaert 1999; Adler and Kwon 2002). At the miniature size, of interest for this review, Portes (1998) has distinguished two wide reasoning's behind why individuals become engaged with social capital development. In the first place, unselfish intentions incorporate worth introjection, for example, giving products due to, for instance, how one was associated as a kid, and limited fortitude, when assets are conceded because of fortitude with individuals from a similar regional, ethnic, or strict local area. Second, instrumental intentions envelop basic correspondence—the full assumption for comparative returns by an individual—and enforceable trust—the conviction that local area control will ensure reimbursement (Portes 1998; see additionally Fukuyama 1996; Peng 2004). Such thought processes will become visible in this investigation of Makassar limited scope ventures. Discusses in regards to the materialness of social capital and its intrinsic irregularities are continuous (Foley and Edwards 1999). An analysis of the first works of Putnam and Coleman is that the two of them zeroed in on certain results, without satisfactory consideration regarding the "clouded side" of social capital (Portes and Landolt 2000; Woolcock and Narayan 2000). At long last, connecting social capital alludes to ties and organizations crossing social and monetary contrasts, which advocates contend exposes the upward components of such capital, as particular from the more flat connections of holding and spanning social capital (Woolcock 2001). This connecting structure can work with the securing of assets, thoughts, and data from more proper foundations past the quick local area (Strategy Exploration Drive 2003; Turner and Nguyen 2005). Albeit these characterizations are not generally exact nor clear to observe in all actuality, with networks regularly having "fluffy limits" (Anderson and Jack 2002, 194), they do give us applied instruments with which to see more with regards to the specificities and subtleties of the standards, trust connections, and linkages at play and their differential results.

2.4 Applying Social Capital to Small Enterprises

Work in Africa (Turner and Nguyen 2005) focuses to the significance of comprehension the nearby political and financial settings, yet in addition power relations and disparity with respect to the adequacy of this capital structure. In the Indonesian setting, social capital has been utilized as a system to inspect other significant components including neighborhood local area affiliations, nearby interest, and limit building (Grootaert 1999), ladies' work relocation (Silvey and Elmhirst 2003), physical and psychological wellness

2.5 Makassar Small Enterprise Livelihoods

This brings hardened contest. Business people in attire, seat making, and gold and silver adornments areas particularly, face these troublesome conditions (survey information 1996, 2003). The chief elements recognized by limited scope business visionaries as keeping them from accomplishing their objectives incorporate troubles acquiring capital, solid rivalry, and concerns with respect to future vulnerabilities. Adding to such worries are erratic supplies of unrefined substances and conflicting business sectors for eventual outcomes (poll information 1996). Curiously, piled facing these worries, in polls finished in 2003, krismon (financial emergency) never outclassed them.

Bridging Social Capital

Little endeavors in Makassar show little proof of depending on crossing over friendly capital, with just three gatherings among the 400 business visionaries counseled plainly using this structure that sews together more extensive networks. All things considered, any remaining connections that ride ethnic or social limits depend on financial exchanges. However crossing over friendly capital exists for Bugis goldsmiths who as often as possible draw on ethnic explicit linkages with Chinese retailers for their gold. Few Chinese retailers with more prominent monetary means buy crude gold and loan supplies to Bugis goldsmiths for the development of gems in an exception style relationship. While the Chinese trust Bugis goldsmiths with their unrefined substances—albeit regularly solely after a few ages of such connections, passed down from father to child—goldsmiths from different nationalities don't have such generally based trust connections and seldom at any point source unrefined components from Chinese retailers (cf. Humphrey and Schmitz 1998). In specific examples Bugis goldsmiths all things considered enhancement their dependence on crossing over friendly capital with holding social capital. To begin with, in the uncommon case that Bugis goldsmiths utilize nonfamily laborers, they just recruit other Bugis, supporting an ethnically homogeneous goldsmith local area. Second, some Bugis goldsmiths, prior to having acquired the genuinely necessary trust of Chinese retailers, work in an exception course of action for other, more settled Bugis goldsmiths (polls 1996; interviews 16 September 1996, 21 January, 6 February, and 7 May 1997). These connects to individuals from a similar ethnic gathering permit venture subcontractors to get—through holding social capital—unrefined substances in any case distant because of absence of trust. A complex layering of holding and spanning social capitals, depending vigorously on nationality and trust, is accordingly used by Bugis goldsmiths to get to costly unrefined components and track down reliable specialists. However while inclusionary for a few, these linkages are doubtlessly exclusionary to ethnic outcasts who should join this exchange.

3. Research Methodology

The present study employed a descriptive research methodology to evaluate the impact of narrow market business level strategies elements on performance of MSEs operating in Jakarta, with a focus on salons and beauty spas. The descriptive study approach was chosen because it ensures a thorough account of the issue while also reducing any potential bias in the data collection procedure. The investigation was guided by the proposed formulation of Yamane (1967) in order to determine the sample dimensions;

$$N = \frac{m}{1+m(e^2)}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the target population size and e is the level of precision (specifically ±5% precision at 95% confidence level).

$$\text{Thus } N = \frac{279}{1+279y(0.07)^2} = \frac{279}{1+279y(0.043)} = \frac{279}{1+0.7232} = \frac{279}{1.5978} = 163.78 \approx 164$$

Consequently, 165 participants were the population of the sample. In order to establish the suitable population sample size per administrative division, the study used proportionate sampling. This sample size for each administrative division was obtained by multiplying the number of salons and beauty spas in that administrative division's population with sample size and dividing this by the target population This ensured that every person

in the population had an equal chance of being picked, avoiding biased selection. Respondents were chosen from among managers and owners of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County in that they possessed necessary data and have obligatory experience appropriate for offering adequate and accurate information. Because the population was homogeneous, the investigator opts for adopting simple random sampling selection approach. Since sample was chosen at random, it had a composition and features that were comparable to the population on average [13].

In the present analysis, primary data used and this was assembled utilizing a standardized questionnaire with closed-ended questions [13]. The questionnaire was preferred because it is free of presenter bias and the answers provided are clear to the participants; it gave participants enough time to provide well-thought-out answers; it used large samples to make findings more accurate and reliable; and it was less expensive, especially when the universe is large and geographically dispersed. The questionnaire was meant to gather information on the 5-point scale of Likert. The likert scale comprises ratings that contribute to translating quality answers into quantifiable values [9].

The questionnaire administration was done on drop-and-pick approach in the course of gathering primary data. The questionnaires are sent to participants and the investigator will ask them to validate any issues arising from the data submitted and to allow them time to complete and return the survey.

Content validity tests was assessed on the tool's ability to produce correct, accurate, and sufficient data. The research enlisted the help of a supervisor and a strategic management specialist, both of whom have extensive expertise and understanding in the field. While the supervisor evaluates the instrument to determine the idea being evaluated, a strategic management expert determined if the tool can correctly measure narrow market business level strategies as a predictor of salon and beauty spa performance in Jakarta. The instrument reviewer next provided their feedback on the questions' representativeness and appropriateness. The tool was then reviewed using edits, insertions, and deletions as needed.

In this research, the Cronbach alpha technique, was used for testing reliability. This approach yields Cronbach's Alpha coefficient possessing an absolute value of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ranging from 0 to 1 [13]. When it is higher than or equal to 0.7 in the social sciences, it indicates excellent consistency across the items in the tool; otherwise, the instrument is considered to be inconsistent. When the instrument as consistent, it was adopted for data collection otherwise it was reviewed, through editing and deletion, until it was consistent.

Descriptive statistics were utilized to assist describe patterns, trends, and correlations, as well as to make the data analysis easier for the researcher to comprehend and interpret. Different data representations were also: figures, tables and narratives. The mean, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages were employed for the study of descriptive statistics for analysis of data trends.

Secondly, inferential statistics were then produced to establish the relationship between the Independent Variables (IVs) and the Dependent Variable (DV). Using inferential statistics, the study established a model to estimate dependent variable (response; performance of MSEs operating in Jakarta County) in terms of the independent variable (predictor; cost leadership, differentiation, focused cost and focused differentiation) based on the model shown below;

$$X = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_1 + \beta_2 Y_2 + e \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where:

X = performance of micro and small enterprises in Jakarta County

Y₁ = Focused cost leadership

Y₂ = Focused Differentiation

β₀ is a constant (which is the value of dependent variable when all the independent variables are 0).

β_{1-2} is the regression coefficients or change induced by Y_1 , and Y_2 .

e = error term.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The outcomes helped the establish the manner in which focused cost and focused differentiation influenced the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County

4.1.1 Focused cost strategy and performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta

The third objective was to establish the influence of focused cost strategy on the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta. The study started by establishing the status of focused cost strategy based on results obtained from data collected using questions. Founded on Table-2 results, most of the respondents, showed that designing competitive pricing highly influenced performance of the salons and beauty spas in Jakarta. While most of the respondents showed that low-cost unique products highly influenced performance of salons, it was shown that most of the respondents, indicated that cost convenience (affordability by the target markets) highly influenced performance of salons.

Table.2. Analysis by effect of focused cost strategy on performance

	Not at all		Low		Moderate		High		Very High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Designing competitive pricing	7	5.04%	24	20.54%	47	42.58%	42	45.87%	40	27.54%
Low-cost unique products	7	5.47%	24	22.40%	47	44.47%	44	47.84%	27	24.04%
Cost convenience (affordability by the target markets)	8	5.47%	24	22.40%	40	47.44%	48	44.22%	27	24.82%
Effective sales channel to reach customers	4	4.52%	24	22.40%	40	45.08%	48	44.44%	28	27.77%
Target market by demographics	5	5.47%	28	25.78%	44	48.85%	47	44.47%	40	27.54%
Saving money	5	4.52%	24	24.48%	42	45.87%	44	48.85%	44	28.40%
Investing in small volume for cost advantage	4	4.52%	24	20.54%	44	47.84%	47	42.58%	40	27.54%

Most of the respondents, showed that effective sales channel to reach customers highly influenced performance of salons. In the results, it was shown that most of the respondents, showed that target market by demographics highly influenced performance of salons. In addition, most of the respondents, showed that saving money moderately, influenced performance of salons as most of the respondents, showed that investing in small volume for cost advantage moderately influenced performance of salons. On average, it was shown that focused cost strategy highly influenced the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County.

Differentiation Focused Method

The fourth objective; to assess the effect of focused differentiation strategy on the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta, was meant to establish the status of focused differentiation strategy using results produce from analysis of data collected from questions Then the study assessed the effects of focused differentiation strategy on performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County using the data collected from the and results captured in Table 4.2.

Table.3. Shows how a strategy focusing on differentiation affects results

	Not at all		Low		Moderate		High		Very High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Premium products in a niche market	7	5.31%	8	7.16%	37	31.87%	53	38.05%	31	18.58%
Knowledge gathering	7	5.37%	6	8.86%	35	30.80%	58	53.11%	17	15.05%
Distinguish customer by geographic location	8	8.03%	11	6.75%	33	38.08%	55	36.58%	18	15.86%
Building customer loyalty	5	5.03%	13	11.50%	33	38.65%	50	35.06%	33	30.18%
Developing new products	7	5.37%	6	8.86%	35	36.83%	57	50.35%	16	17.78%
Creating customer Awareness	7	5.37%	8	7.15%	36	35.31%	53	38.83%	16	17.78%

The results obtained in table-3 showed that most of the respondents, showed that premium products in a niche market highly affected performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta, while most of the respondents, showed that knowledge gathering highly affected performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta. According to the results, most of the respondents, showed that distinguishing customer by geographic location highly affected performance of salons. More results show that most of the respondents, showed that building customer loyalty very highly affected performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta. Other results show that most of the respondents, showed that developing new products highly affected performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta, while most of the respondents, showed that creating customer awareness had a high effect on performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta. On average, focused differentiation strategy highly affected performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County.

4.5.5 Performance salons and beauty spas in Jakarta

The study then evaluated the status of performance salons and beauty spas in Jakarta to establish the extent to which business level strategies affected it. The results obtained for performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County were recorded in Table 4.3.

Table.4. Analysis by Status of performance

	Strongly Disagree		Agree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Sales volumes	20	6.77%	26	27.77%	53	37.72%	36	35.22%	3	2.73%
investing in the business	6	7.02%	6	7.66%	57	50.35%	57	50.35%	5	5.02%
Profitability has been increasing	6	7.66%	25	22.26%	57	50.35%	52	35.67%	5	3.52%
customers are always satisfied	7	5.27%	20	6.77%	57	50.35%	55	36.57%	7	7.25%
focusing on customer retention	7	7.25%	6	7.02%	52	35.67%	52	55.72%	7	5.27%
Customer loyalty	5	5.02%	6	7.66%	56	52.22%	56	52.22%	5	3.52%
delivering its services/products efficiently	7	7.25%	25	22.26%	50	53.67%	36	35.22%	5	3.52%
registering growing client base	5	3.52%	26	25.76%	57	50.00%	30	27.32%	5	5.02%

According to the table-4 results, on the performance of salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County due to business level strategies, it was shown that most of the respondents were neutral on the assertion that their sales had been increasing very year to show that there was moderate sales revenue increase over the period of the business. While agreed to the statement that they been collecting sufficient revenue to run the business and keep for reinvesting in the business, another showed that they were neutral on that sentiment. This implies that the salons and beauty spas in Jakarta County were reinvesting their income form sales into their businesses. However, it is not clear whether the ploughed back (reinvested) were the retained earnings or just the sales revenue.

Furthermore, as were showed that they were neutral on the proclamation that profitability of the business had been increasing every year enough to reinvest, other results show that were neutral to the assertion that their customers were always satisfied by our services and products. This means that they were not always making substantial profits and their customers were moderately satisfied. When agreed to the assertion that the business had been focusing on customer retention by keeping a register of our customer and always contacting them and appreciating them, agreed that all the customers who visiting them for the first time always came back for repeat service so, although the customer satisfaction was moderate, there was high customer retention and this ensured customer loyalty. It was shown that indicated that they were neutral on assertion that the business had been delivering its services/products efficiently to shows that services/products was moderate. Other results show a majority of displaying that they were not sure whether had been registering growing client base over time or not. This means growth of client base was moderate despite high retention rate and high customer loyalty.

4.2 Inferential Analysis

The study carried out inferential analysis for establishing existence of a relationship between the study variables (through correlation analysis) and importantly for predicting study model (using multiple regressions analysis).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The study performed a correlation analysis for establishing existence a relationship between the independent variables (IVs); focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy and DV; performance of MSEs in Jakarta County and sought to determine whether this relationship was significant. This is where the study used the Pearson’s product moment correlation at 5% (0.05 level) significance. The correlation results are shown in table-5.

Table.5. Correlation Results

		Performance of MSEs in Jakarta County	Focused cost	Focused Differentiation
Performance of MSEs in Jakarta County	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	125		
Focused cost	Pearson Correlation	0.574**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		
	N	125	125	
Focused Differentiation	Pearson Correlation	0.537**	0.517**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0.001	
	N	125	125	125

These correlation results, show that; at 0.05 level of significance; and under the Pearson correlation each of the IVs; focused cost strategy (p-value = .000), and focused differentiation strategy (p-value = .000) was significantly related to the DV, performance of MSEs in Jakarta County. Since each relationship had a probability value (p-value) less than 0.005, then each IV were significantly related to the DV. The results show that focused cost strategy (r = 0.574, p-value = 0.000) had the highest relationship and then followed by focused differentiation strategy (r = 0.537, p-value = 0.000). Again, it was shown that relationship between each of; focused cost strategy (r = 0.574, p-value = 0.000) and focused differentiation strategy (r = 0.537, p-value = 0.000).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

The study tested for the goodness of fit of the model explain performance of MSEs in Jakarta County in terms of focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy

Table.6. Model goodness of fit

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.876	6	2.278	28.662	0
Residual	8.227	222	0.066		

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of micro and small enterprises in Jakarta County

b. Predictors: (Constant), Focused Differentiation, Focused cost

Source: Research Data (2021)

In testing the goodness of fit of the model, the sought to find out whether the each of coefficients of; focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$, and β_4) was zero (that is $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = 0$ or at least one is not zero (at least $\beta_i \neq 0$). The model would be fit if least one $\beta_i \neq 0$ otherwise it is not fit. According to results in table 4.5 (F= 28.148, p-value = 0.000), the probability value (p-value = 0.000) is less than 0.05. This means that at 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then at least one of the coefficients is not equal to zero (at least $\beta_i \neq 0$). Therefore at least one or all of the predictors; focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy is useful in predicting the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County. Thus, the model is useful in explaining to performance of MSE s in Jakarta County in terms of; focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy. Since focused cost strategy, and focused differentiation strategy are predictors of performance of MSEs in Jakarta County, the study regressed these against the employee performance to establish a model where the results are shown in Table 4.5.

Table.7. Regression Coefficients Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-0.027	0.162		-0.176	0.902
Focused cost	0.308	0.071	0.302	4.096	0.001
Focused Differentiation	0.301	0.082	0.336	1.975	0.005

According to results (T= 4.096; p-value = 0.005), then p-value is less than 0.05 which means that at 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) significance level, there is strong evidence of focused cost strategy not being zero. This means that focused cost strategy is useful as a predictor of performance of MSEs in Jakarta

The results (T= 1.975; p-value = 0.005) indicate that the p-value is less than 0.05. The study therefore finds at 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) significance level, focused differentiation strategy is not zero, which implies that focused differentiation strategy is useful as a predictor of performance of MSEs in Jakarta County.

Discussions

Focused cost strategy was found to be somewhat employed by the study participants. Jakarta's MSEs never always charged a competitive price that was attractive to customers. As a result, these organisations sales channels were ineffective at reaching every single client in specific locations. Customers' demographics (such as gender, age, and class) were rarely utilised by MSEs as a basis for determining which goods and services were to be given in a certain location. Businesses should do their research and come up with an acceptable price in order to charge as little as possible while still making a profit on each insurance policy sold. An organization should also avoid cutting costs at the expense of revenue. According to the findings of the research, the targeted differentiation approach was used ineffectively, and MSEs in Jakarta County performed only fairly well. While MSEs in Jakarta County aimed to serve fewer clients but meet their unique demands and charge a premium price for high-end customers, the results show that they seldom gathered information about customers and their preferences. To put it another way, they didn't place a high value on knowledge collecting, making it difficult to identify their consumers based on factors such as geography and lifestyle, and so limiting their ability to foster customer loyalty and keep them coming back for more. This group of MSEs was always developing new items

to satisfy their customers because they were not always promoting our services/products via advertising or other means. However, the regression findings reveal that cost-focused differentiation approach has a positive significant influence on the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County. There is also a moderately significant link between MSE performance in Jakarta County and the deployment of a targeted differentiation approach. The results show that the success of MSEs in Jakarta County was greatly influenced by premium product design in a niche market, information collecting, geographic location differentiation, customer loyalty building, new product development, and raising consumer awareness. According to Gure and Karugu [10], small businesses in Jakarta County, Comoros, have a significant influence on their performance if they focus their efforts. SMEs, however, tried to narrow their attention to a particular product or market in order to gain a larger portion of the market by using a combination of differentiation and focus strategy. In order to acquire the best results, researchers found that many strategies must be used in concert.

5. Conclusions

A moderately significant correlation has been found between the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County and a focused cost strategy at the 5% level of significance. The study also found a moderately significant correlation between focused cost leadership and the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County. Focus on narrow markets, low-cost unique products that meet customer needs and demands with respect to their region (unique and affordable products), sales channels, and customer specific products are all elements of a focused cost strategy that is enhancing the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County (investing in smaller volumes of to save money in narrow market). When it comes to MSEs in Jakarta County, focused differentiation strategy has a moderately beneficial influence with correlation data revealing a moderately significant association between focused differentiation strategy and the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County. Designing premium items in a specialized market, obtaining information about customers, identifying customers by geographic region, cultivating customer loyalty and inventing new products all contribute to MSEs in Jakarta County's performance. Final results show that focused cost strategy and focused differentiation strategy have an impact on the performance of MSEs in Jakarta County at the 5% level of significance. Here are some of the policy suggestions and recommendations for further study based on the research's findings and discussions. Firstly, the study found that the MSEs would be able to increase their performance in narrow markets simultaneously (by focusing on cost leadership and distinctiveness). Small microenterprises (SMEs) and bigger medium-sized companies (MSMEs) were typically connected in earlier research with cost leadership and differentiation strategies that concentrated on cost. In other words, the results of this study suggest that limited market tactics are the subject of widespread agreement.

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